

EXAMINING THE TIME MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF MANUFACTURING ENGINEERS TOWARD OPERATIONAL EXCELLENCE

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ABSTRACT

Time management is crucial to ensuring that manufacturing operations run smoothly and efficiently. Manufacturing engineers play a key role in achieving operational excellence, and as such, it is important to examine their time management practices. The purpose of the qualitative research is to gain insight into the time management strategies employed by manufacturing engineers in pursuit of operational excellence. Through a qualitative research method, the study aims to examine the strategies used by manufacturing engineers in time management, the challenges they face in doing so, and the benefits of time management to achieving operational excellence. Semi-structured interviews with ten manufacturing engineers with extensive experience in operational excellence were conducted. The interviews were recorded, transcribed, and analyzed for themes using a thematic analysis approach. The study revealed that manufacturing engineers use different time management practices to achieve operational excellence. These practices included delegation of tasks, setting priorities, scheduling, and time tracking. However, the study had unraveled several significant challenges experienced by manufacturing engineers in managing their time effectively, including interruptions, conflicting priorities, and workload. The study also uncovered several benefits of effective time management for achieving operational excellence. These included increased productivity, reduced stress levels, enhanced decision-making, and better work-life balance. Furthermore, the findings of the study can be utilized in designing training and support systems that can aid manufacturing engineers in utilizing effective time management strategies toward operational excellence. The research findings lend credence to the notion that effective time management is fundamental in achieving operational excellence in manufacturing.

Keywords: *Time Management Practices, Operational Excellence, Engineering Management, Qualitative, Thematic*

INTRODUCTION

Nature and Scope of the Problem Investigated

In today's fast-paced and highly competitive industrial landscape, achieving operational excellence had been critical for organizations to stay ahead of the competition. One of the key factors that contributed to operational excellence was effective time management practices. (Ruane, 2022). Unfortunately, time as a critical factor in manufacturing seems to be treated flexibly: as if it can be adjusted and adapted to changing circumstances without incurring serious consequences. The concomitant problem in mismanaging time was dreadfully demonstrated in the case of the Boeing 737 Max. In this case, the company's rush to release the aircraft to the market resulted in serious time management issues that ultimately resulted in two fatal crashes. Manufacturing engineers played a crucial role in achieving operational excellence as they are responsible for ensuring the smooth operation of production processes. Effective time management practices were essential for manufacturing engineers to ensure that they meet production targets and deadlines, maintain quality, and optimize resources. The field of manufacturing engineering was concerned with the design, development, and implementation of efficient and effective production systems. One of the key challenges faced by manufacturing engineers was ensuring that production processes were completed within the designated time frame, while maintaining high levels of quality and minimizing costs. Engineers worked hard to reduce any waste of time, money, materials, energy or other commodities by streamlining procedures and processes. This was achieved through the application of special knowledge and skills to specify, predict, and evaluate results from processes and systems. The purpose of this study was to explore time management practices of manufacturing engineers toward operational excellence using phenomenology.

The research questions and objectives are as follows:

Table 1. Research Questions and Objectives

RESEARCH QUESTIONS	OBJECTIVES
1. What are the lived experiences of manufacturing engineers in employing time management practices contribute to operational excellence?	Identify the underlying beliefs, attitudes, and motivations of engineers that influenced their time management practices, and how these practices contributed to operational excellence.
2. What do manufacturing engineers prioritize to effectively manage their time?	Identify and understand the key factors that engineers consider important when managing their time in order to improve productivity, efficiency, and overall performance in their roles.
3. What mechanisms do manufacturing engineers adopt and perform to balance	Determine the strategies that engineers employ to effectively manage the

time constraint against the planned scope and cost of work?

interplay between time constraints, planned scope, and cost considerations in their work.

4. What approaches do manufacturing firms use to address how organizational culture affects the time management practices of manufacturing engineers?

Determine the impact of organizational culture on the time management practices of manufacturing engineers.

The study has significant focus on the following:

Theory: This research was anchored on theory about Theory of Constraints (TOC) is a management philosophy developed by Eliyahu M. Goldratt in his 1984 publication, "The Goal: A Process of Ongoing Improvement." A constraint is something that limits an individual's performance, and this theory assumes that there was always at least one constraint.

Policy: The findings of the study can provide insights into the time management practices of production engineers, which can inform policies and guidelines for optimizing production processes in various industries.

Practice: The study's findings can be beneficial to manufacturing engineers in enhancing their time management skills and achieving operational excellence by identifying the challenges and opportunities for improvement.

Social Contributions: The study can contribute to the broader understanding of the importance of time management practices in achieving operational excellence, which can benefit society by promoting more efficient and effective production processes.

The theoretical framework used was the Theory of Triple Constraints or the Project Management Triangle. (see Figure 1.)

Figure 1: Triple Constraint Theory

The main component of the triple constraint theory was that scope, time and cost were interwoven aspects of any project that every manufacturing engineer was working on. When one changes the other two must be changed as well. This means if the timeline changes the scope and cost must change and if the scope changes the cost and timeline must change. Together, it represented the most important factors in completing a project properly as everything else falls within these three broad categories. (Liyanage, 2021)

The study provided light on manufacturing engineers' capacity for managing project schedules, met deadlines, and efficiently allocated time to diverse activities by studying how they dealt with the time constraint of the Triple Constraint Theory. When achieving operational excellence was time-sensitive, this inquiry also revealed potential obstacles and engineering approaches. It provided a structured framework to investigate the complex interaction between time management techniques, project outcomes, and operational excellence, and acted as an anchor for this study.

The conceptual framework (see Figure 2) illustrates that time could be the factor that was least flexible for being difficult to adjust and almost impossible to retrieve when wasted.

Figure 2: Time is critical and the least flexible in the Triple Constraint Theory

Operational excellence (O/E) equates with quality and therefore serves as a foundation that enables equilibrium when the scope, cost, and time constraints were balanced. By streamlined processes, eliminated waste, and increased efficiency, operational excellence helps reduce the time and cost required to complete a project. By achieving operational excellence and ensuring quality, project managers can help to deliver projects that meet the three constraints of time, cost, and scope. Significant factors that must be balanced in order to successfully complete a project.

Table 2. Definition of Terms

TERM	DEFINITION
Cost of Work	The sum of the costs of all resources consumed in the process of making a product. Classified into three main categories: direct materials cost, direct labor cost, and manufacturing overhead. (Samani, 2022)
Eat That Frog Technique	Identifying and tackling the most important or challenging task early in the day, known as the "frog." By prioritizing and completing this task first, the technique aimed to increase productivity, build momentum, and create a sense of accomplishment that carries through the rest of the day.
Getting Things Done (GTD)	Capturing all tasks and commitments, clarifying their nature and next steps, organizing them in a systematic manner, reflecting on priorities, and ultimately engaging with tasks in a productive and efficient manner.
Lived experience	Personal knowledge about the world gained through direct, first-hand involvement in everyday events rather than through representations constructed by other individuals.
Pomodoro Technique	Dividing work into timed intervals of focused activity, followed by short breaks. The technique aimed to enhance productivity, maintain focus, and prevent burnout by providing a structured rhythm for work and rest.
Scope of Work	A descriptive document or working agreement that contained all information regarding the size of a project, the goals a team should accomplish by the end of the project and steps required to complete the project. (Indeed Editorial Team, 2023)
Triple Constraints Theory	Stated that every project involved three constraints that can affect the outcome of the entire project. The so-called triple constraints of project management were the budget, time and scope. Each of these constraints affected the entire project if met poorly by the project managers. (Opinaldo, 2022)

Review of Pertinent Literatures

Time management skills started at the academic level of an individual, according to the research of Ahmad, N., & Mansoor, B. (2017). As it examined the relationship between time management practices and academic performance among college students. The

study found that effective time management practices were associated with better academic performance, and that the relationship was partially mediated by procrastination.

Additionally, Ismail, N. H., Ismail, W. K. W., Abdul Rasid, S. Z., & Osman, M. S. (2019), investigated the relationship between time management practices and job performance among employees in a Malaysian manufacturing company. The study found that effective time management practices, such as setting goals and managing interruptions, can enhance job performance and improve overall operational excellence. Furthermore, Lin, L., Chen, M. H., & Kao, C. (2013) examined the relationship between employee training and operational performance in a manufacturing company. The study found that effective time management practices, such as task prioritization and workflow analysis, were positively associated with employee training and can lead to increased operational excellence. Moreover, Hosseini, S. M., Dehkordi, G. J., & Sabet, E. A. (2019), investigated the relationship between time management practices and employee performance in the automotive industry. The study found that effective time management practices, such as setting goals and managing interruptions, improved employee performance and enhanced operational excellence.

Based on the literature and studies cited, it was clear that effective time management practices were critical towards achieving operational excellence in the manufacturing industry. However, achieving operational excellence through time management practices depended on certain factors and conditions. One factor was the implementation of time management tools and techniques. Many studies found that implementing time management tools and techniques, such as visual management and standard work, supported the implementation of lean manufacturing practices, improved operational efficiency, reduced lead time, increased output, and reduced downtime. Therefore, manufacturing companies need to identify the appropriate time management tools and techniques that fit their unique needs and circumstances. Achieving operational excellence through time management practices depended on the appropriate implementation of time management tools and techniques, availability of time management training programs, and supportive organizational culture and management support.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a phenomenological research design that explored the lived experiences of manufacturing engineers regarding time management practices. It involved semi-structured interviews that gathered in-depth data about their lived experiences and perceptions of time management practices. It focused on manufacturing, production, and allied engineers in maintenance, technical, quality, and safety departments of companies with an existing certified quality management system to share their lived experiences about what it was like to work in a company that sought, achieved, and sustained

operational excellence. These companies were located in industrial parks in Laguna, Philippines which were in the food and beverage, automotive paint, semiconductor sectors only. The following criteria were used: manufacturing engineers who had at least two years of experience in the field; worked in a manufacturing or production environment; responsible for managing and improving production processes; involved in time management practices and work towards achieving operational excellence. The chosen criteria fitted the objectives and methodology effectively, resulting in a study sample that was narrowly focused and pertinent.

The study used thematic analysis and interpretative phenomenological analysis together that provided a highly detailed analysis of the experiences of manufacturing engineers in relation to time management practices toward operational excellence. It allowed the development of a more comprehensive understanding of this phenomenon. The interview took around 30 – 60 minutes depending on the flow of the discussion. The data analysis and plan were shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Data Analysis Matrix

RESEARCH QUESTIONS	OBJECTIVES	RESEARCH METHOD	SOURCE OF DATA	DATA ANALYSIS
1. What are the lived experiences of manufacturing engineers in employing time management practices that contribute to operational excellence?	Identify the underlying beliefs, attitudes, and motivations of engineers that influenced their time management practices, and how these practices contributed to operational excellence.	Interview	Key Informant Interview	Thematic Analysis (TA) And Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)
2. What do manufacturing engineers prioritize to effectively manage their time?	Identify and understand the key factors that engineers consider important when managing their time in order to improve productivity, efficiency, and overall performance in their roles.	Interview	Key Informant Interview	Thematic Analysis (TA) And Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)
3. What mechanisms do manufacturing engineers adopt and perform to balance time constraints against the planned scope and cost of work?	Determine the strategies that engineers employ to effectively manage the interplay between time constraints, planned scope, and cost considerations in their work.	Interview	Key Informant Interview	Thematic Analysis (TA) And Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

4. What approaches do manufacturing firms use to address how organizational culture affects the time management practices of manufacturing engineers?	Determine the impact of organizational culture on the time management practices of manufacturing engineers	Interview	Key Informant Interview	Thematic Analysis (TA) And Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)
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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The core concept of the first research inquiry revolved around the tangible encounters of manufacturing engineers as they implement strategies for managing time. These experiences and the conclusions generated from the interviews were closely related. The topics that surfaced, "Adaptability and Consistency," were strongly aligned with the research question. These ideas highlighted how crucial it is to strike a balance between meticulous planning and project completion. The idea that manufacturing engineers must find a dynamic balance between organized time-management techniques and the capacity to handle unforeseen obstacles made this link clear. In a similar fashion, the theme of "Life Integration" mirrored the essence of the research question. It underscores the aspiration for a harmonious equilibrium between work and personal life, which the engineers' actual experiences and approaches significantly contributed to. Consequently, the recognized themes of adaptability, life integration, and career navigation served to shed light on and validated the exploration of the research question, which delved into manufacturing engineers' actual experiences with time management practices.

The goal of the second research question, which was to understand the priorities that manufacturing engineers set for their time management, was closely aligned with the themes that emerged from the interview replies. The themes that were found, such as "Efficient Task Tracking and Prioritization," captured the substance of the research topic by concentrating on the essential idea of task management and organization optimization to increase productivity and accomplish objectives.

The third objective of the research question, which centered around matching time constraints with the anticipated scope and expense of work, was closely related to the themes found in the interview replies. The themes that had been found, such as "Detail-oriented Project Oversight," were consistent with the study question because they highlighted the need of paying close attention to project details and effective monitoring as key elements in managing time restraints against project scope and expense. This theme emphasized how crucial it was to comprehend every project component in order to ensure correct scope and cost management.

The last research question, aimed at comprehending the influence of organizational culture on the time management practices of manufacturing engineers, found a clear resonance with the themes uncovered from the interview responses. The themes that

have been found, such as "Collaborative Project Management," supported the research issue by demonstrating how organizational culture may promote teamwork, communication, and alignment—all essential components of efficient time management approach. It resonated with the research question by emphasizing how organizational culture cultivated a sense of accountability and professionalism in meeting deadlines, which directly influenced time management practices. Lastly, the theme of "Productive Time Assessment" corresponded with the research question by highlighting the significance of time management skills that were influenced and shaped by the organizational culture, ultimately leading to more efficient allocation of tasks and achievement of business objectives. In summary, the identified themes vividly illustrated how the organizational culture directly influences and shapes manufacturing engineers' time management practices, thereby closely connected with the research question's core inquiry.

Research Implications

The results of this study shed light the key factors that influence organizational success.

A. The interconnected themes of efficient time management, effective task tracking, prioritization, teamwork in project management, and overcoming productivity barriers were crucial for boosting productivity, operational excellence, and goal achievement inside companies.

B. Engineers and organizations optimized their processes, promoted success, and improved overall performance by carefully examining and comprehending these elements. Engineers and organizations make considerable progress toward achieving success and have a positive effect in their respective industries by adapting the knowledge obtained from this research.

This study offered insightful information that can instruct and direct experts in the manufacturing sector toward better time management techniques, which ultimately resulted in increased productivity and operational excellence.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were formulated:

1. To explore the real-life experiences of manufacturing engineers concerning their implementation of time management practices.

Organizations showed efficient adjustment to changes and unforeseen obstacles while still assuring continuous and dependable delivery of goods or services by acknowledging the requirement for flexibility and adaptability. Engineers maximized their productivity and made optimal use of their time and resources by

using time blocking strategies and setting realistic goals. Lastly, engineers improved the quality of their work and boosted productivity, by eliminating errors, allocating effort optimally, improving efficiency, and encouraging continual development.

2. To understand the priorities set by manufacturing engineers when managing their time.

The existence of unforeseen events and technical difficulties were troublesome. These unexpected difficulties call for flexibility and problem-solving abilities. Meeting deadlines not only ensures timely project completion but also fosters professional growth, builds trust, and drives organizational success.

3. To balance the constraints of time against the planned scope and cost of their work.

Engineers can optimize their productivity, achieve better results, and navigate through various challenges with confidence. It was possible to implement effective planning and proactive risk mitigation methods by having a thorough understanding of the potential effects of hazards.

4. To understand how organizational culture affects the time management practices of manufacturing engineers.

Engineers optimized project oversight and drive successful outcomes through comprehensively understanding project details, utilized a daily activity log, and prioritized tasks effectively. Engineers ensured that urgent activities are completed on time by allocating their resources and efforts in accordance with the urgency of each assignment.

And lastly, engineers can discover opportunities for development and take the required steps to keep on track by monitoring key performance indicators (KPIs) tied to organizational goals.

Time management, task monitoring, prioritization, collaborative project management, overcoming productivity barriers, and attaining the best results were all necessary for organizational success.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the study recommends the following:

1. A mixed-methods approach or including a more diverse and representative sample can be used to increase the external validity of the findings.

2. The study may be limited by the small sample size, which might reduce the statistical power and alter how reliable the results are. As a result, care should be taken when interpreting the findings, and additional research with bigger sample sizes is advised to increase the dependability of the conclusions.

3. Future researchers should make sure that their data analysis procedures are transparent, use several analysts to cross-validate the findings, and go by accepted research standards and protocols in order to reduce this constraint.

4. Future research should use a more comprehensive approach, taking into account a wider variety of variables and their interactions.

5. Future research should use a more comprehensive approach, taking into account a wider variety of variables and their interactions., namely in the areas of job function, responsibility, and accountability.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher complied with the basic standards of research ethics and also followed the Data Privacy Act in the collection and process of data gathered.

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